

Contesting Israel's "New" Middle East Project

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In his January 1991 State of the Union address, a few months after Iraq invaded Kuwait, US President George H.W. Bush proclaimed a “new world order” [Bush 1991]. An energy-dependent US, free of Cold War constraints, sought to dominate the wider Middle East by destroying the Iraqi armed forces and infrastructure, crippling Iraq with sanctions, and then establishing a hegemonic security architecture with military bases across the region. Its main goals were to secure control of Gulf oil and, starting with the Bill Clinton presidency, to prioritize Israeli interests above all others in the region.

The Middle East has since absorbed two major dynamics to re-shape the region: the US push to re-engineer recalcitrant states after 2003 and the Arab uprisings’ people-centered mass mobilization against authoritarian regimes starting in 2010. Each of these dynamics has pitted contradictory forces seeking order transformation against those fighting for order maintenance, and each has yielded unexpected results creating new actors and further instability.

Today we are witnessing a third such re-ordering dynamic precipitated by the post-October 7 genocidal war in Gaza and the dismantling of the Iran-led regional alliance. Israel, with total support from the US, is

attempting to redraw the Middle East map to ensure its regional primacy and accommodate its expansionist project, and to force an end to the Palestine question. The success of this Israeli project, however, is uncertain in the longer-term as it requires constant violence to pacify oppositional regional actors; proactive blocking of international and regional consensus to achieve stability through negotiations, particularly with Iran; and the continuation of unqualified US support.

To understand the current emerging regional order, with all its uncertainties, we need to first frame it within the broader context of the other two regional transformations that led respectively to Iran and Turkey’s rise (along with their attendant regional allies) and to the corresponding insecurity of America’s main allies in the Gulf and Israel. Social changes across the region, particularly in Saudi Arabia and Israel, over this time also played a key role, along with the structural change in American power and the gradual shift away from a US “rules-based” order to a more competitive global one.

The first Middle East re-ordering dynamic started in the context of the post-2001 US “war on terror,” where Iraq, once again, was at the center of a renewed “imperial moment for America” (Sick, 2002). Led by hardline and

staunchly pro-Israel neoconservatives, the US dismantled the Iraqi state and ushered in a regional transformation project to forcibly re-engineer states that, like Iraq, had not fully submitted to American, or Israeli, hegemony. These included Lebanon, Palestine, Syria and the biggest prize of all, Iran (Clark 2007).

The neocon project was eventually defeated by a counterinsurgency against US occupation forces in Iraq and resistance forces in Palestine and Lebanon, where Israel, acting as America's proxy, failed to achieve its declared objective to crush Hizbullah in its 2006 war on Lebanon (Makdisi 2011). Instead, Hizbullah leader Hassan Nasrallah emerged as the most popular leader across the Arab world, and Iran's regional ascendancy was confirmed. US failure in Iraq and Iran's growing counterbalance to US/Israel hegemony in the region, embodied through an "Axis of Resistance," set up a two-decade rivalry with an increasingly insecure Saudi Arabia that feared the weakening of protective US security architecture.

The second re-ordering dynamic in the Middle East emerged from the Arab Uprisings that started in late 2010 in Tunisia and then spread across the region (Makdisi 2017). Unlike the neoconservative project, this attempt at order transformation was initially more people-centered (Sadiki 2016) and triggered popular mobilization led by increasingly influential non-state players such as the Muslim Brotherhood (Hazbun 2015). With US President Barack Obama seeking to pivot away from the Middle East, regional actors, particularly Turkey, started acting more autonomously to assert their influence (Boserup et al 2017).

With the established US regional order under threat, counter-revolutionary forces led

primarily by Israel, Saudi Arabia, and the UAE supported the suppression of popular forces from Egypt to Palestine. Their central goal was to contain a perceived "neo-Ottoman" Turkish-Qatari project aiming to transform regional security dynamics and dominate post-uprising societies through national Muslim Brotherhood projects (Caffero 2019). Saudi-Turkish relations entered a decade-long regional "confrontation" (Ulrichsen 2022), and official Israel-Turkish relations deteriorated, at least performatively, to reflect huge popular support for Palestinians and Turkey's desire for legitimating its leadership position across the Islamic world.

Concurrently, during this second re-ordering period, core Axis members, comprising Iran's Revolutionary Guards, Hizbullah, and Iraq's Popular Mobilization Units (PMU), formed their "first wartime coalition" in 2013 to intervene militarily in defense of the Syrian state—pivotal to the Axis's regional viability—that faced both a popular uprising of its own and a Gulf, Western and Turkish-sponsored armed rebellion (Saad 2024). This wartime Axis coalition consolidated further by supporting the PMU's fight in Iraq against the Islamic State, Yemen's Ansar Allah (Houthi) war against a Saudi-led coalition, and Hamas and Islamic Jihad's resistance against successive Israeli invasions of besieged Gaza. Meanwhile, in Lebanon, Hizbullah built up a huge arsenal of sophisticated weaponry and Hassan Nasrallah became the de facto regional leader of the Axis.

On the eve of October 7, 2023, then, America's main regional allies in the Gulf and Israel felt increasingly insecure at the prospect of a multipolar regional configuration that would include Iran and Turkey within the context of a perceived diminishing influence of the US. The latter appeared intent on establishing a

regional security architecture less reliant on direct US military involvement and more on building a regional coalition to contain Iran, maintain some form of Palestinian self-rule (albeit on shrinking territory), and normalize Gulf-Israeli relations, embodied most visibly in the 2020 Abraham Accords. This official US intent was consistent throughout the respective terms of presidents Obama, Trump, and even Biden until after October 2023.

While the Saudis and Israelis, during this time, both resented Iran/Axis's and Turkey's (with Qatar) respective rise and feared potential US disengagement, they took different paths to adapt to these changes. While the Saudis moved towards diplomacy, the Israelis continued to agitate for war to settle the regional balance of power.

Shaken by the American nuclear deal with Iran and US inaction when Yemen's Ansar Allah targeted key Gulf infrastructure like Saudi Aramco, Saudi perception of a diminishing US security architecture incentivized more self-reliance (Baabood, 2024). Saudi Arabia, now benefiting from the rise of China and focusing on national development policies, gradually moved under MBS from a violent and punitive approach against perceived regional foes—including waging a brutal war on Yemen and laying siege on Qatar—to a strategy of accommodating Iran and Turkey to stabilize the region. In March 2023, Saudi Arabia and Iran announced a Chinese-brokered reconciliation agreement normalizing relations and opening the way for regional de-escalation, starting in Yemen. Significantly, the US welcomed this deal. Saudi Turkish relations, meanwhile, moved towards rapprochement after 2021.

For its part, Israel, dominated by Benjamin Netanyahu and his extremist partners since

2009, agitated for regional war and accused the US of “abandoning” it following the Iran nuclear deal and the unprecedented abstention in a UN Security Council resolution demanding a halt to all settlement construction in occupied Palestinian territory (Cortellessa 2016). It also felt threatened by Saudi-Iranian rapprochement and efforts to settle regional disputes diplomatically. At the same time, Israel increasingly became an international pariah state, losing the “legitimacy war” to the Palestinians and the global solidarity movement (Falk 2021). The UN and major international human rights organizations called Israel out as an “apartheid” regime, while the International Court of Justice investigated Israel's unlawful occupation and settlement policies, and the International Criminal Court opened an investigation into Israeli war crimes. Finally, a deeply divided Israel was increasingly at war with itself, pitting religious extremists and their messianic project to fulfill an expansionist “Greater Israel” against a more secular one trying to block a theocratic state and accepting that, in the words of former Israeli Prime Minister Ehud Olmert, “Greater Israel is over. There is no such thing” (Ravid 2008).

It is against this backdrop that we can better contextualize the unfolding struggle for a third re-ordering of the region. This struggle was arguably *inevitable* for two main reasons. On the one hand, the regional projects represented respectively by the Axis and Greater Israel grew to become fundamentally mutually exclusive. On the other hand, the US failed, or was unwilling, to stabilize the region by complying with international/ Arab League consensus, and Arab popular demands, on Palestinian self-determination and, after Obama, recognizing the multipolar regional reality.

If October 7, 2023, represented Hamas' and later the broader Axis' desire to re-center the region around the Palestine question (in its strategic, political and humanitarian dimensions) and re-orient it away from normalization deals, then Israel's long-standing objective under Netanyahu and his extremist coalition is to use October 7 for two main goals that would, in Netanyahu's own words, redraw the Middle East map (Berman et al 2025). Its first goal is to ethnically cleanse Palestinians, by any means necessary, including genocide (UN 2024), and erase Palestine from the map (Tharoor 2023). Its second goal is to transform the region and expand its territory by crushing Iran's regional ambitions and the Axis' resistance to a Greater Israel.

The US position has, over the past year, reversed its policies of the past 15 years by accommodating Israel's ethnic cleansing of Palestinians, most recently via the "Trump Plan" for Gaza to "get a beautiful area to resettle people, permanently" (Al Jazeera 2025). The US is also pushing to impose normalization agreements on Lebanon and Syria that would represent capitulation deals (Jawad 2025). These deals would require acceptance of the changed Middle East map and the unilateral right of Israel to police the region through drone attacks and high-tech surveillance. With the Gaza war signaling the demise of the liberal international order and its constraints on the use of force, non-compliance with these US-Israeli deals in this new dystopian reality means collective punishment of the civilian populations with impunity.

If effectively using unfettered hard power by the US and Israel to defeat the Axis—with Iran weakened regionally, Hizbullah severely degraded in Lebanon and Bashar al Assad overthrown in Syria—represented one pillar of apparent success for this Israeli-led re-or-

dering project for the Middle East, then Saudi and Mashriqi normalization with Israel and the completion of the ethnic cleansing of Palestinians is the other crucial pillar needed to complete this re-ordering.

There are at least three challenges to Israel's project, however.

The first is a clear tension between the US's two main regional allies: Israel and Saudi Arabia. Israel's plan to complete its genocide in Gaza, annex Palestinian lands in the West Bank, and push Palestinians into neighboring Arab states directly contradicts Saudi Arabia's (and Arab consensus') clearly declared desire to stabilize the region via normalization deals that would require recognition of a Palestinian state. Saudi Arabia, like all Arab states, is constrained by the overwhelming support for Palestinians across the Arab world and popular opposition to normalization. Moreover, Saudi Arabia's renewed engagement with Iran and its strong support for US-Iranian negotiations over a nuclear deal to enhance "peace in the region and the world" (Nereim 2025) is in direct contradiction to Israel's plans to attack Iran and draw in direct US military involvement. While Trump clearly wishes to pursue US interests via negotiations and nuclear deal with Iran, intense lobbying by neocon elements within his administration supports Israel's desire for war (Barnes et al 2025). The outcome of this struggle within the Trump administration will have a major impact on the region.

The second challenge to this re-ordering is the potential reassertion of Palestinian—and Lebanese (and potentially Syrian)—agency and resistance to an Israel that has never been as dependent on the US as it is now. The reality is that during its war on Gaza, Israeli forces failed to achieve their declared objective

of militarily defeating Hamas, just as Israel failed to advance in southern Lebanon as Hizbullah fighters successfully mounted fierce resistance against all odds. The Houthis in Yemen, meanwhile, continue to block Israeli shipping despite unprecedented attacks by the US on behalf of Israel. While the Axis may have been defeated in regional terms, local resistance may well grow again, even as solidarity with Palestinians and popular opposition to Israel continues to increase in the US despite the unprecedented violent crackdown on free speech and dissent by the Trump administration.

The third main challenge is represented by the resurgence of Turkish regional ambitions following the collapse of the Assad regime in Syria. Despite close relations between Israel and Turkey in security and trade terms, there is a fundamental clash in regional interests between a Turkey that aspires to lead the Muslim world and a Greater Israel project. Syria now represents the battleground for a potential clash as each carves up a sphere of influence there, and this may well spread.

Given so much uncertainty, not just regionally but globally as well, it is impossible to predict if the Israeli-US re-ordering of the Middle East will succeed or if the many challenges—including obvious contradictions between Israeli and US interests, and new resistance forces that will emerge—they face in accomplishing their goals will constrain them and potentially create yet further unpredictable regional dynamics.

What we can be sure of is that we are in a moment of rupture, and that international consensus on regional diplomacy and the resolution of the Palestine question has a far greater chance of achieving stability than the neocon/Israeli push for further war. ♦

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